
Workplace Stressors: Impact on Job Stress Among Nurse Educators in the Southeast Nigeria Universities

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ABSTRACT

Workplace stress among health educators is becoming an emerging issue in the global world today, and its effect becomes more pronounced in the Nigerian setting. This study determined the impact of workplace stressors on nurse educators in the southeastern universities' nursing departments in Nigeria. A cross-sectional study design was used; a purposeful sampling technique was employed to select 10 accredited universities offering nursing in south-east Nigeria, and a census method was adopted to arrive at a sample size of one hundred and seventy-six (176) based on the small size of the nurse educators in the selected universities. Data was collected with a self-administered questionnaire, collated and analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. The democratic managerial style had 148 (84.09%) acceptances in this study; the respondents (172, 97.7%) accepted that interpersonal relationships with colleagues can influence job stress and that lack of special training or skills is not a challenge to nurse educators in the selected university nursing departments. The hypothesis testing revealed that the calculated p-value was less than the 0.05 significance; hence, all the work stressors tested have a significant relationship with job stress.

KEYWORDS: Workplace stressors, impact, Job stress, nurse educator, Southeast universities

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INTRODUCTION

Job stress is an employee's mental state aroused by a job situation or a combination of situations perceived as presenting excessive and divergent demands ¹. Job stress refers to a mental and physical condition which affects an individual's productivity at the workplace, as well as his effectiveness, personal health and quality of work ^{1,2}. Concepted job stress as a "universal element that is not only encountered in individual but also in every organization regardless its size". While some perceived stress as negative energy some embraces it as a motivator ^{4,5,11}. However, Job stress seems to correlate with conditions within the workplace; meaning job stress is a ruminant of individual experience at workplace and a discomfort or unpleasant emotion experienced by a teacher ⁶; one may ask, what are those conditions in the university that cause stress among nurse educators

Nursing education remains crucial in the production of competent health practitioners in Nigeria as the need for skilled nurses increases with time. ^{7,8,9}. Educators play a significant part in the education of nurses and are tasked with the responsibility of bringing to their pupils the skills and attitudes that enable competent practice ¹⁰. There are various problems in the field of nursing education, such as lack of adequate resources, imbalance between students and nurse educators and the increasing demands of curriculum changes ^{11,7,12}. All these factors contribute significantly towards stress at work amongst nurse educators.

Despite the critical importance of nurse educators in healthcare delivery, limited research has been conducted to explore the specific job-related factors that influence their stress level within Nigeria and universities, especially in the southeastern region. Understanding the job correlates such as workload, role conflicts, organisational support, and professional development ^{13,14}, can provide valuable insight into the source and impact of job stress. This knowledge is essential for developing targeted interventions aimed at improving job satisfaction, reducing stress and enhancing the overall effectiveness of nurse educators. Consequently, this study seeks to fulfil the existing knowledge gap by examining the relationship between various job correlates and job stress among

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nurse educators in Southeastern Nigerian universities, thereby contributing to policy formulation and institutional strategies for a healthier and more productive academic workforce.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What is the correlate between managerial style and job stress among nurse educators in Southeast universities' nursing departments in Nigeria?
2. What is the influence of interpersonal relationship with colleagues on job stress among nurse educators in Southeast universities' nursing departments in Nigeria?
3. What is the correlate between lack of special training/skills in nursing education and job stress among nurse educators in southeast Nigeria.?

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1. There is no significant influence of interpersonal relationship with colleagues on job stress among nurse educators in southeast Nigeria.
2. There is no significant relationship between lack of special training/skills in nursing education and job stress among nurse educators in southeast Nigeria.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A cross-sectional descriptive survey design was adopted, and an adapted self-administered questionnaire to meet the objective of the study was used for data collection. A purposeful sampling technique was employed to select 10 out of 12 universities offering nursing in southeast Nigeria based on inclusion and exclusion criteria, respectively, with a census method for a sample size of 176 due to the manageable population size of the nurse educators in the selected universities.

The instrument has 51 items. Section A assessed respondent socio-demographic information, while Section B elicited the relationship between variables using a Likert-like 5-point scale (5 = strongly agree, 4 = agree, 3 = uncertain, 2 = disagree, and 1 = strongly disagree) to assess the relationship between the variables.

Validity and reliability of the instrument.

After adapting stress evaluation tools by Shea and De-Cieri (2016), they were put to a test (pilot study) using 18 copies (a tenth of the sample size), and responses from a sister university in Benin, Edo State, Department of Nursing, were analysed to arrive at a Cronbach's alpha of 0.8, which is considered satisfactory.

One hundred sixty-seven (176) respondents filled out and returned their questionnaire within 60 days of administration and collection of the questionnaire.

The returned and collated questionnaire was analysed, using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software, version 26. Pearson's correlation coefficient and chi-square at the 0.05 significance level were used to establish the relationship between the variables under study in hypotheses 1 to 5. Items with a mean score > 3 were accepted as variables impacting job stress, while those < 3 were rejected.

RESULT

Table 1: Managerial Style/Support as a cause of job stress among Nurse Educators

Items	Likert scale					Mean score	Remark
	Strongly Agree (5)	Agree (4)	Neutral or Uncertain (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)		
Managerial style more predominant in your department is democratic or empowering leadership.	24(13.64)	124(70.45)	9(5.11)	14(7.9)	5(2.8)	3.8	Accept
Managerial style more predominant in your department is autocratic leadership.	8(4.55)	9(5.11)	16(9.09)	104(59.1)	39(22.2)	2.1	Reject
Managerial style in your department is a cause of job stress to you.	7(3.98)	32(18.18)	15(8.52)	90(51.14)	32(18.2)	2.3	Reject
You cannot rely on your head of department to help you out with work problem.	7(3.98)	30(17.05)	4(2.27)	92(52.27)	43(24.43)	2.2	Reject

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You are not supported through by your head of department in emotionally demanding work.	2(1.14)	8(4.55)	10(5.68)	109(61.9)	47(26.7)	1.9	Reject
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Mean score < 3 Rejected, >3 Accepted.

From Table 1, Majority (84.09%) of the respondents accepted democratic leadership as the predominant (mean score of 3.8) managerial style in their departments, while other items have a mean score less than 3 independently, hence, were rejected

Table 2: Interpersonal relationships as a cause of job stress among nurses Educators

Items	Likert scale					Mean score	Remark
	Strongly Agree (5)	Agree (4)	Neutral or Uncertain (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)		
Interpersonal relationship with colleagues can influence job stress.	104(59.1)	68(38.6)	2(1.1)	2(1.14)	0	4.5	Accept
You get help you need from your colleagues at work.	23(13.1)	138(78.4)	10(5.7)	3(1.70)	2(1.14)	4.0	Accept
There is friction or anger between colleagues in your department.	9(5.11)	93(52.8)	24(13.6)	36(20.5)	14(8.0)	3.2	Accept
Relationship with colleagues at workplace are strained or poor	2(1.1)	75(42.6)	31(17.6)	53(30.1)	15(8.5)	2.9	Reject
Poor interpersonal relationship with colleagues can contribute to job stress.	101(57.3)	73(41.5)	2(1.14)	0	0	4.5	Accept

Mean score < 3 Rejected, >3 Accepted.

Table 2 shows that the item, relationships with colleagues at workplace are strained or poor have negative responses with a mean score of 2.9, while other items, interpersonal relationship with colleagues can influence job stress, you get help you need from your colleagues at workplace, there is friction or anger between colleagues in your department, and poor interpersonal relationship with colleagues contributing to job stress were all agreed on with positive mean scores of 4.5, 4.0, 3.2 and 4.5 respectively. This implies that poor interpersonal relationship poses a challenge, and it is a cause of job stress among the respondent.

Table 3: Lack of Special Training/Skills as a cause of job stress among Nurse Educators

Items	Likert scale					Mean score	Remark
	Strongly Agree (5)	Agree (4)	Neutral or Uncertain (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)		
You are not clear about duties and responsibilities assigned to you.	1(0.57)	33(18.9)	4(2.3)	100(57.6)	38(21.7)	2.1	Reject
You did not receive specialty training related to your teaching area or course.	5(2.84)	44(25.00)	0	85(48.3)	42(23.9)	2.3	Reject
You are feeling not well trained/incompetent for job doing.	3(1.70)	27(15.34)	2(1.14)	94(53.41)	50(28.41)	2.2	Reject
Lack of specialty training/skill is a cause of job stress to you.	13(8.00)	44(25.1)	9(5.14)	68(38.9)	40(22.9)	2.5	Reject
Lack of specialty training affects your ability to teach and supervise students.	19(10.80)	39(22.16)	3(1.70)	68(38.6)	47(26.7)	2.5	Reject

Mean score < 3 Rejected, >3 Accepted.

Table 3 shows that the items 'not clear about assigned responsibilities', 'no special training received in area of teaching or course', 'feeling incompetent on the job assigned', and 'lack of special training being a cause of stress and affecting their ability to teach and supervise students' were unanimously disagreed with, with negative mean scores of 2.5 and below; hence, mastery of job/special training or skills is not a challenge to nurse educators in the selected university nursing departments.

Null Hypothesis 1: There Is No Significant Influence of Interpersonal Relationship with Colleagues on Job Stress Among Nurse Educators in South East Nigeria.

Table 4.: Influence of interpersonal relationship with colleagues on Job stress among Nurse educators in South East Nigeria.

Interpersonal relationship with colleagues	Job stress (%)		X ² -value	p-value
	Low level (n=43)	High level (n=133)		
Good	5 (11.63)	0 (0.0)		
Poor	37 (86.05)	68 (51.13)	40.88	<0.001
Very Poor	1 (2.33)	65 (48.87)		

/=significant p-value<0.05/*

Table 4 shows the chi-square result of interpersonal relationship with colleagues versus job stress. It revealed a calculated p-value of 0.001 which is less than 0.05 p-value tabulated, therefore, H0 ~~was rejected~~not accept, butthus accept H1 was accepted that there is a significant influence of Interpersonal relationship with colleagues on job stress among nurse educators in southeast Nigeria.

Null Hypothesis 2: There Is No Significant Relationship Between Lack of Special Training/Skills in Nursing Education and Job Stress Among Nurse Educators in South East Nigeria

Table 5: Relationship between lack of Special training/skills in Nursing education and Job stress among Nurse educators in South East Nigeria

Lack Of Special Training/Skills	Job stress (%)		X ² -value	p-value
	Low level (n=43)	High level (n=133)		
Good	41 (95.35)	74 (55.64)		
Poor	1 (2.33)	26 (81)	22.63	<0.001*
Very Poor	1 (2.33)	33 (24.81)		

/=significant p-value<0.05/*

Table 5 on lack of special training/skills versus Job stress, the result shows a calculated p-value of< 0.001 which is less than 0.05, and it is statistically significant. Therefore, we accept H1 that there is a significant relationship between lack of special training/skills in nursing education and job stress among nurse educators in departments of nursing science of universities in southeast Nigeria.

DISCUSSION

The correlate between managerial style and job stress among nurse educators in Southeast universities' nursing departments was expressed to be democratic leadership by 84.09% of the respondents. Having this type of leadership where the nurse educators are fully involved in activities and decision-making in the department proved that managerial style as a factor in this study is not a major cause of stress among nurse lecturers. This finding contradicts that of ¹⁵, whose UK study revealed managerial practice as a common cause of job stress. In Nigeria nursing is a female-dominated profession even in the academic setting and job stress is the most common health issue observed in many organizations', particularly among women ¹⁶. Having a democratic leadership style where nurse educators can air their views and be involved in decision-making may reduce job stress. The differences in the reports may be due to the type of managerial style dominant in the study areas. For example, democratic leadership will cushion the effect of stress on workers, while autocratic leadership will create more stress to nurse educators.

The study revealed a unanimous agreement by respondents (98.89% and 97.70%) that relationships among educators can influence job stress. This finding corroborates that of ¹⁷ in Indonesia, whose study revealed a strong relationship between interpersonal relationships among lecturers and work stress. This study also revealed having poor interpersonal relationships contributes to job stress among nurse educators. This challenge was also overcome in ¹⁷ study because the educators in the study had a good

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interpersonal relationship with their workplace; hence, they got necessary assistance from colleagues when needed. Therefore, a nurse educator with a chronic inability to establish and maintain healthy, stable relationships with colleagues may develop workplace job stress. In other words, a healthy interpersonal relationship enhances communication and cooperation.

Lack of special training/skills in nursing education, as a cause of job stress among Nurse Educators in South East Nigeria.

Findings from the study show that the majority of the respondents (61.80% and 65.30%, respectively) agreed that lack of special training/skills is not a cause of job stress among them, and lack of special training/skills does not affect their ability to teach or supervise students. This showed that lack of special training/skills in nursing education is not a major cause of job stress among nurses. Educators in departments of nursing science of the universities in Southeast Nigeria. This result disagrees with McVicar, in ³, whose study identified insufficient skills or lack of specialty training as one of the factors that commonly cause work-related stress. The findings were also incongruent with those of ¹⁸, whose study revealed the need for skill training for proper integration of ideas and subjects when delivering lectures. Nurse educator experience may be gotten by exposure to different skills which promote a better understanding of the job demand and resources available for use ¹⁹, hence, lessening job stress. The differences in the findings may be due to the level of education of the respondents and experiences as well as individual differences concerning special training/skills across the globe. For example, a nurse educator who specialises in maternal and child health nursing will demonstrate mastery of teaching and the use of the course register, making the imparting of knowledge easier, while an individual that lacks special training in the same field may be stressed out by the same job.

Regarding the hypotheses, the two variables' calculated p value was less than 0.001, which showed that workplace stressors (interpersonal relationships and lack of specialty / training skills) tested for a relationship with job stress all have a significant relationship with job stress. These findings are in line with ¹⁷, who reported a strong relationship between interpersonal relationships and job stress. This implies having a good or bad rapport with individual colleagues at the workplace can impede or promote job stress independently. The similarity might be that across the globe. Moreover, workplace stressors and job stress are inevitable in any organization, however, when workplace stressors and job stress come into play, employees may find it difficult to concentrate, meet deadlines, and utilise their creativity ²⁰. On the other hand, workplace stressors may be a motivator.

CONCLUSION

This study found that workplace factors play an important role in shaping the level of job stress experienced by nurse educators in universities in Southeast Nigeria, and the democratic leadership style is commonly practiced. Interpersonal relationships with colleagues significantly influenced stress levels. Training- and skill-related factors had significant relationship with job stress. Fostering supportive work environments, encouraging healthy professional relationships, and providing ongoing professional development opportunities could help reduce stress and improve the well-being and productivity of nurse educators.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors of this study declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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